

New Architecture of Storage for Network Security and Identify Data Security Issues in Cloud Computing

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 16, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Network Security issues, Cloud Computing, Data Storage, RAID, Network Security</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4597647</p>	<p><i>Cloud Computing (CC) is regarded as a worldwide outward-looking infrastructure that is highly open to computers. The key to CC, in economic terms, is that customers are free to use whatever they want and pay for the services they want. The accessibility of cloud resources can be achieved whenever users want and wherever they are. Users are therefore free to buy the IT service they want, and they do not have to worry more about how sustainable things can be beyond their positions. Users can use services in other ways by simply plugging into the cloud and only paying for what they use. All these features have become very useful and challenging for cloud computing. However, data privacy is a key security problem in CC which involves data integrity, privacy, and user privacy. Most people do not prefer cloud data to be saved because they are worried that their sensitive data will be lost. This study aims to recognize various issues of cloud computer data protection and architecture for secure cloud storage such that personal data are encrypted and divided up into some cipher blocks and spread between different websites of services providers instead of relying exclusively on a single data storage provider.</i></p>

Introduction

Grid computing, distributed computing, parallel computing, virtualization, utilities, and other computer technology are all derived from the word cloud. CC enables users to connect to a huge, shared computer pool that is offered to them as a service, similar to a power grid that allows users to "plug in the cloud." A computer model like this allows for server consolidation and cost reduction by scale savings. CC was the next generation of computing (Wentao, 2012). In the CC environment, all software and resources are available on demand from the Internet as services. Cloud is a hardware and software resource environment in data centers, providing varied network or Internet services in order to meet user requirements consumers can be liberated from the often-boring task of maintaining and supplying computer resources to run apps thanks to the cloud (Wang et al., Privacy-preserving public auditing for secure cloud storage. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 62(2), pp.362–375., 2013). The cloud also provides a range of other advantages, such as (1) a pay-as-you-go cost model that allows users to pay only for what they use. (2) The ability to use software more efficiently and quickly; (3) a dynamic and elastic supply of resources, which means that, unlike traditional data centres, there is no need to ensure maximum loads because applications can expand and reduce processing; and (4) a stronger and safer, highly usable, and elastically scalable infrastructure. All of these cloud features are offered at no extra cost to consumers, although at the same time. All of these cloud features are available to users at no extra cost, while still giving them a great deal of versatility in how they use and provision computing tools (Sonam, 2013). Computing, storage, and other specification facilities may all be called tools. CC can be regarded as a modern archetype of computing that provides resources on demand at low prices. Software as a service (SaaS), platform as a service (PaaS) and infrastructure as a service are the three well recognized and widely used services in the cloud model (IaaS). In SaaS, a cloud service provider deploys software that contains the associated data, and users can access it through the web browsers. In PaaS, a service provider provides customers services that can cater for tasks through a series of software programs. In IaaS, the cloud service company offers virtual machines and computing facilities for customers in order to develop their business skills. The security issues of users should be answered first to make the CC trustworthy by users and businesses. The stable environment is a fundamental precondition for users' trust in the implementation of such a technology (Zhao et al., 2015). Latif et al. discussed cloud risk assessment. Users can access their apps and data from everywhere through just two things, internet connection and a software on their device for CC systems as easy as a web browser, from any device. CC has a number of beneficial features, but cloud security problems remain one of the key barriers of CC adoption. The protection of user data is one of the key concerns of cloud computing. The data are not really secure in cloud storage, since they are saved as public place for service providers. However, many daunting issues of security have also been brought to the attention of users, as is cloud computing. The biggest problem of protection is that the location of the owners' data is not tracked. It is not safe in CC to rely on a single data

storage service provider (Sr & Sharma, 2016). In the services provider location, any network or hardware problems cause the data to be lost, so the data can be recovered from this structure via distributed parity system and the Redundant Collection of Inexpensive Disks (RAID) store schema. Data propagation over several clouds was addressed using a system which can be disrupted in one network by an adversary. The key focus of CC was the RAID storage technology. The encryption quota is not able to fulfill the confidentiality demanded by cloud computing, as the confidentiality of information in CC is inadequate. Instead of central dissemination, the notion of the distribution of information over multiple cloud services providers was put forward. The cloud storage framework requires an input layer, an interface layer. There have been debates about the combination of cloud storage and private cloud (Qusay et al., 2018). It suggested structure of cloud storage, concealing hardware and software complexities from its operators. Hadoop-centric secrecy cloud storage application advantages and feasibility have been evaluated. As the universal standard among service providers and service users, the Service Level Agreement (SLA) has been used to ensure information security in the cloud storage system (Dillon et al., 2010). It was proposed that the user information be kept firmly in open cloud and secluded cloud with encryption. Cloud storage security subjects were analyzed based on cloud and landscape perceptions.

2. Literature Review

Security challenges in the CC and issues that different researchers discuss. The CC Use Cases group discusses the various scenarios in the CC model for use and related requirements (CCUCDG, 2010). They look at cases from a variety of perspectives, including clients, developers and security engineers. ENISA has investigated the risk, likelihood of risks, effects and vulnerabilities in CC that could result in such risks, in connection with the introduction and adoption of cloud computing. CSA's "Top Threats to Cloud Computing" discussed similar initiatives. The security SLA specifications and goals of data location, segregation and recovery are discussable by Balachandra et al., (2009). Popovic et al., (2010) discuss high-level security issues such as data integrity, payment and privacy in the CC model. Popovic et al., (2010) has discussed various security management standards including ITIL, ISO/IEC 27001 and Open Virtualization (OVF) (ENISA, 2009). Jensen et al., (2009) talk about the technical security issues resulting from cloud-based model adoption, such as XML attacks, related browser attacks and flood attacks. (Grobauer et al., 2010) talked about the cloud platform security vulnerabilities. The authors grouped the potential vulnerabilities into technology-related, cloud-related security checks. Cloud service delivery challenges of the SaaS model. CSA discusses key areas of cloud computing. They provide the cloud provider, consumers and security vendors with a set of best practices to follow in every domain. For some of these domains, CSA has produced a number of detailed reports. In our research, we conducted a profound investigation in the cloud model in order to determine the root causes and key dimensions of security problems discussed during the previous work. This contributes to a better understanding of the problem and solutions.

3. The CC Architecture and Security Implications

There are three models of CC and three models for deployment. The implementing models are: (1) Private cloud: a cloud platform for a specific company; (2) Public cloud: a cloud platform that can be used and registered by public users; and (3) Hybrid cloud, a private cloud that can use resources in public clouds. Public clouds make their services the most vulnerable, possibly malicious. The models for the provision of cloud services as shown in figure (1) include the following - IaaS: where cloud providers provide computing resources, storage and networking as internet-based services. The Virtualization Technology is a service model. The most well-known IaaS provider is Amazon EC2. - Cloud providers provide platforms, tools and other commercial services which allow customers not to install any of these platforms, or tools to supported them on local machines to develop, deploy and manage their own applications. The PaaS model can be located directly above the IaaS model or above the cloud infrastructure. The most popular PaaS are Google Apps and Microsoft Windows Azure (Microsoft, 2018).

Software-as-a-service (SaaS), where cloud providers provide cloud-hosted applications for end-users as an internet service, without requiring customers to install applications. Software as a service (SaaS) – SaaS security terms are negotiated with the CSP as part of the service agreement. SaaS often hosts the physical, infrastructural, hypervisor, network traffic and operating system of an undertaking. SaaS applications and controls on infrastructure may include: Implement prevention of data loss (DLP), Prevent unauthorized data sharing with incorrect persons, block corporate data sync / download on personal equipment, Detect affected accounts, insider and malware threats, Gain visibility for non-supported applications, Mistake Audit (Wang et al., Open Identity Management Framework for SaaS Ecosystem," in ICEBE '09, pp. 512-517., 2015). This model can be hosted on PaaS, IaaS and cloud infrastructure, directly. Platform-as-a-service (PaaS) – The CSP is responsible for the protection of its Applications and guarantees that a majority of its cloud service model is protected. PaaS builds on IaaS, without the expense and resources to purchase and maintain hardware, software and hosting functions. These characteristics can include: Security brokers for Cloud Access (CASB), Security platforms for cloud workload (CWPP), Control of Cloud Protection (CSPM), Intelligence/Business Analytics, Logging, IP constraints, Ports for API, Internet for industry (IoT). An example of the SaaS provider is Salesforce CRM. The

different possible implementations of each service delivery model complicate the development of standard models of security for each service delivery model. In addition, these models may coexist on one cloud platform to make the security management process even more complicated.

Figure 1: cloud service delivery models

4. Security Issues

The security of data is one of the most important issues for any storage architecture. Although cloud providers have dominant facilities and security mechanisms for the safety and availability of customized data, in recent years several reports on data privacy have been published. Consumer services like e-mail, social networks, and virtual worlds are among the most visible cloud applications today. These services' providers capture terabytes of data, including classified information, which is then stored in data centers around the world. In addition to the data storage on one single service provider site, we have distributed data among existing service providers to ensure the security of customer data. Architecture suggested. Data availability is accomplished by redundancy where and how the data are stored. Data stored on any storage system depends on the speed at which data is accessed. The network channel bandwidth is subject to accessibility. For data storage, high speed network cables are used. The implementation of the proposed architecture at RAID level also provides greater data availability. However, as suppliers provide the customer with cloud storage services, normally on the internet. This generates a variety of user protection and confidentiality issues about their data. Access: in cloud the possibility of accessing confidential user information is very high. These issues include Access: In the cloud world there are even more opportunities for computer data theft. Hackers and malicious intruders will access cloud accounts and steal sensitive cloud-based data. A company person may also open and illegally alter confidential data. This jeopardizes the privacy of the data. The cloud system will deploy the cloud center in various areas and store data in various Cloud nodes. The various fields of law have various rules such that the danger of the law can be met. User control: the specifics of service delivery, infrastructure and management can be hidden as a cloud system. They do not contain any information as to location of data, servers and networks, due to the simplicity and scalability of the cloud system. They do not include data. Because of that, users are unable to track the progress of the data handling process, which makes the user confidentially unaware of their cloud data protection and privacy. The power over how the information is stored, limits on who can get access to it is available on the conventional PCs or servers operated by a corporation or a person. Data is saved on the server for CC and the third-party provider decides on data storage information. It is the duty of the service provider to manage user data, but it is a legal obligation of the user to control their data when processed or stored. Failure to trust: Cloud Provider does not have an audit process to track the user's internal data protection transactions. How a user makes sure his data is secure without proof. In Cloud, the user and the provider do not trust. Lack of trust is the main cause which prevents different organizations and peoples from adopting the cloud. Cloud is mobile and complex, since the legal obligation of protecting the protection of confidential information imposed on the cloud by the consumer is not straightforward. This also leads to a lack of cloud trust. Legal security can also boost the CC service.

5. Analysis of System Storage Architecture

We discuss safety and efficiency of our proposed architecture in this section. One of the key problems is to safeguard the data stored in the cloud storage. The service provider can be truthful, but malicious users trigger safety issues. It is a major threat to sensitive data such as medical and financial information, since the host data is open to cloud service providers. We encrypt the original data and then distribute the fragments transparently across multiple service providers to resolve the security problem. In this way, none of the storage providers has the customer's data at all. The key thing to do is store data on a variety of cloud storage providers, with no full copies of the data in one place and just a subset of providers to restore the data. The efficiency of the parity method is accomplished by allowing the application to correctly retrieve data even though some of the providers corrupt or lose data.

6. Conclusion and Future Directions

In this paper, we have introduced a new web-based data storage and management generation that uses remote

servers. In cloud computing, the paradigm to tackle the troublesome problem is the protection of data stored on the web of service providers. The new protected data storage architecture enables user data to be encrypted and split into different cipher blocks and distributed between different service providers sites, not depends solely on a single data storage provider. This architecture guarantees greater trust, availability, scalability, and protection. This paper shows also cloud principles, models, and services, which show that cloud capabilities are autonomous, low-cost, and reliable, such as scalability, elasticity, and platform. The reliability, availability, scalability, efficiency, and robustness of such models are to be discussed in the next directions of this review. An additional important factor to be explored is the development of a business model that reasonably charges the SPs for these storage facilities. Talk about CC data protection issues and the solutions to address them in such a way that users' trust in the cloud is enhanced and data security is made clear.

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